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VIRTUAL ECCI AND DISLOCATION DENSITY TENSOR

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Abstract	Dislocations create elastic fields, detectable by surface-sensitive techniques like EBSD and ECCI. In this report, a field dislocation mechanics (FDM) model to compare surface and bulk dislocation signatures in GaN layers on Si substrates is used. Significant differences between surface and bulk fields highlight potential misinterpretations in surface-based dislocation characterization. Metrics for accurate dislocation characterization and perform virtual ECCI are established.
Keywords	Threading dislocations, modeling, fast Fourier transforms, GaN, ECCI, elastic fields, EBSD, GND, Nye density tensor, free surfaces.

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Executive Summary

Dislocations are crystal line defects that induce long-range elastic fields inside materials. These dislocations can significantly alter the positions of atoms near the defects, enabling their detection through surface-sensitive electron diffraction techniques, such as electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) or electron channeling contrast imaging (ECCI). In this report, we explore the effect of free surfaces on dislocation elastic signatures, by comparison with bulk signatures, in order to assess the possible influence on dislocation detection and characterization using surface diffraction-based techniques. To this end, we employ a field dislocation mechanics (FDM) model numerically approximated by a fast Fourier transform (FFT) based algorithm, which allows to model any dislocation configuration with the effect of free surfaces. In addition to strain, rotation and stress fields, the model is further used to generate virtual curvature and associated geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) density maps that can be typically measured in EBSD to characterize dislocations. We apply the framework to threading dislocations in GaN semiconductor [0001] direction layers deposited on a Si substrate. This represents both a model material system for the present study, and an assessment of the possible applicability of EBSD and ECCI to characterize various threading dislocations in GaN layers. Our findings reveal that the simulated fields can differ significantly between the surface and the bulk, which can lead to potential misinterpretation in dislocation characterization when using experimental surface-based techniques like EBSD. Additionally, our findings establish essential metrics (strains, rotations, GND density) for the precise characterization of dislocations both at the GaN surface and within the bulk. These metrics are crucial for performing virtual ECCI, which aligns simulation data with experimental observations.

Executive Summary

Abbreviation / Term	Definition
ECCI	Electron channeling contrast imaging
EBSD	Electron backscatter diffraction
FDM	Field dislocation mechanics
FFT	Fast Fourier transform
GaN	Gallium nitride
LEDs	light-emitting diodes
RF	Radiofrequency
SiC	Silicon carbide
GND	Geometrically necessary dislocation
TDs	Threading dislocations
SSD	Statistically stored dislocation
SEM	Scanning electron microscope
EBSP	Electron backscatter diffraction pattern
FFTW	Fast Fourier transform of the west
DFT	The discrete Fourier transform
u	Dislocations line
b	Burgers vector
α	Nye tensor
U^e	Elastic distortion
w	Elastic displacement vector
σ	Cauchy stress tensor
C	The fourth-order elastic stiffness tensor
ε^e	The elastic strain tensor
Γ^0	The modified Green tensor
ξ	The Fourier frequency vector
$\bar{\sigma}$	macroscopic imposed stress
e_n	The stress equilibrium convergence criterion
g	diffraction vector
ω	Rotation

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Chapter 1 Introduction

Gallium Nitride (GaN) is an important wide bandgap semiconductor material that has gained an immense interest due to its exceptional physical and electronic properties. With a bandgap of approximately 3.4 eV (Yam, et al. (2011)). GaN is particularly suited for high-power, high-frequency, and optoelectronic applications (Nakamura, S., & Fasol, G. (2013)). These include blue and ultraviolet light-emitting diodes (LEDs), laser diodes, and high-performance transistors used in radiofrequency (RF) systems and power electronics (Nakamura, S., & Fasol, G. (2013)). Its ability to operate under high temperatures and voltages makes it indispensable in advanced electronic devices. Despite its advantages, the fabrication of GaN faces significant challenges. A critical issue is the absence of a lattice-matched substrate (suitable gallium nitride (GaN) substrate). This forces the adoption of heteroepitaxy, typically on sapphire, silicon carbide (SiC), or silicon substrates. Such misfit growth results in high densities of defects, predominantly threading dislocations, with densities ranging from 10^6 to 10^{10} cm^{-2} (Yam, et al. (2011)). These dislocations adversely affect the performance and longevity of GaN-based devices by creating non-radiative recombination centers, which reduce optical efficiency and increase leakage currents in electronic devices (Speck, J. S., & Rosner, S. J. (1999)).

Research into the behaviour of dislocations near free surfaces has revealed important phenomena, such as the concept of the image force. When a dislocation is located near a free surface (with a maximum distance of 80 nm), a fictitious "image dislocation" is introduced conceptually, mirroring the real dislocation on the opposite side of the surface. The interaction between the real and image dislocation creates an image force that drives the dislocation toward the surface. This phenomenon, leading to enhanced dislocation migration and annihilation at free surfaces, reducing the material's internal defect density. (D. Hull and D.J. Bacon. (2011)).

To detect and characterize dislocations near free surfaces, Advanced surface-sensitive electron diffraction techniques, such as Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD) and Electron Channeling Contrast Imaging (ECCI), have proven indispensable. EBSD allows for high-resolution mapping of crystallographic orientation, enabling the visualization and characterization of defect density distributions within microstructures, while ECCI reveals dislocations by generating channeling contrast, making it especially effective and non-destructive for identifying threading dislocations (Zaefferer, S., & Elhami, N. N. (2014)). Therefore, our research specifically investigates the free surface, more specifically, our focus is to explore how the presence of a free surface alters the elastic fields surrounding threading dislocations, and how these modified elastic fields differ from those in the bulk material, in order to assess the possible influence on dislocation detection and characterization using surface diffraction-based techniques.

These elastic fields provide valuable insights into the fundamental nature of dislocations, enhancing our ability to characterize and classify them both at the surface and within the bulk of the material. Beyond classification, we aim to establish a robust framework for conducting virtual Electron Channelling Contrast Imaging. By correlating simulation data with the expected contrast variations in ECCI, we strive to develop precise metrics that will facilitate the interpretation of dislocation configurations in both experimental and virtual environments.

To model dislocation structures in a three-dimensional material effectively, we employ a Field Dislocation Mechanics (FDM) approach, as developed by (Acharya, A. (2001)). This model interprets discrete dislocation lines as continuous, spatially distributed densities. Dislocations are characterized by the Nye tensor α (Nye, J. F. (1953)), also referred to as "geometrically necessary" dislocation (GND) density tensor in the literature. A notable advantage of this FDM model is its approximation by a fast Fourier transform (FFT)-based numerical algorithm, which allows to model realistic 3D dislocation configurations with the effect of free surfaces.

We focus our study on threading dislocations in GaN semiconductor [0001] direction layers deposited on a Si substrate. As outputs, the model provides elastic fields, such as strain, rotation

and stress. It is further used to generate virtual curvature and associated geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) density maps.

The structure of this report is organized as follows. we start with an introduction, outline the objectives and scope of the study. chapter 2 focuses on the threading dislocations in GaN. Chapter 3 introduces the elasto-static Field Dislocation Mechanics (FDM) model, along with the equations and the FFT-based algorithm used for the numerical approximation. In Chapter 4, the chosen setup and configuration are presented, then we delve into the elastic fields and define the essential metrics required for the effective characterization of dislocations, as well as the implementation of virtual Electron Channelling Contrast Imaging. Finally, the report concludes with a summary of the key findings and implications.

Chapter 2 Threading dislocations in GaN

GaN films must be deposited on substrates like sapphire, silicon, or silicon carbide, using vapor deposition methods in a heteroepitaxial growth process (Kwong et al., (2011)). Depending on the lattice and thermal expansion differences with the substrate, GaN can experience either compressive or tensile biaxial strain. This strain in the GaN epilayer is relieved through the formation of threading dislocations (TDs), which originate at the interface between the substrate and the GaN nucleation layer (Kapolnek et al., (1995)). TDs may be classified as $\langle a \rangle$ -type ($\mathbf{b} = 1/3 \langle 11\bar{2}0 \rangle$) i.e. edge, or $\langle a+c \rangle$ -type ($\mathbf{b} = 1/3 \langle 11\bar{2}3 \rangle$) i.e. mixed, or $\langle c \rangle$ -type ($\mathbf{b} = \langle 0001 \rangle$) i.e. screw dislocations. The direction of the dislocation line \mathbf{u} is either parallel to $[0001]$ i.e. the growth direction, as seen in edge and screw TDs (Moram et al., (2009)) i.e. or approximately 12° from it, as in mixed TDs (see Figure 1) (Mandal et al., (2024)). the angle (\vec{b}, \vec{u}) provide as the nature of dislocation.

The formation of screw and mixed TDs is complex, and their density decreases as film thickness increases, due to the ease of cross-slip (Kapolnek et al., (1995)). Studies suggest that dislocation density decreases further with the formation of half-loops as the GaN film thickness grows. While TDs form to relieve lattice misfit strains, they cannot be entirely eliminated. These dislocations, especially screw TDs, serve as nonradiative recombination centers that can degrade emission intensity and may increase leakage currents (Speck, J. S., & Rosner, S. J. (1999)). Therefore, identifying and characterizing TDs is essential to achieve desired material properties.

When an ensemble of dislocation lines is measured and characterized in a given volume of observation, e.g. a pixel in a EBSD scan, one defines a dislocation density. Dislocation densities are classically categorized into statistically stored dislocation (SSD) densities, where all dislocations statistically compensate each other to yield a null net overall Burgers vector, and geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) densities, where dislocation lines form a polarized pattern and yield a non-zero overall Burgers vector (Voyiadjis & Peters, (2010)). Dislocation ensembles can be seen as SSD or GND densities, depending on the scale of observation. The larger the scale of observation, the greater the SSD density as compared to the GND density, while a single dislocation is a GND by definition.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of different types of TDs with all possible dislocation lines and Burgers vectors, and also a dislocation loop showing all possible lines and Burgers vectors; E: edge ($\langle a \rangle$ -type), S: screw ($\langle c \rangle$ -type), M: mixed ($\langle a+c \rangle$ -type). MANDAL, Arka, et al. Estimation of dislocation densities with non-destructive SEM techniques: application to GaN, 2024. (under review).

Chapter 3 Surface characterization techniques in the

SEM: ECCI and EBSD

3.1 Electron channeling contrast imaging – ECCI

Electron Channeling Contrast Imaging (ECCI) is a scanning electron microscopy non-destructive technique that uses a backscatter electron detector to visualize lattice defects, such as dislocations, near the surface of bulk samples. ECCI can typically probe a depth of approximately 100 nm on centimeter-sized bulk specimens within an SEM. Although “ECCI” is a relatively new term, the use of backscattered electrons to image crystallographic contrasts in samples has been used for many decades. In the 1970s and 1980s, electron channelling patterns (ECPs) were used for the crystallographic analysis of materials science and geological samples in the SEM, with the same approach used for the collection of “channelling micrographs”. As EBSD became an established technique in the 1990s, researchers started utilising backscattered electron (BSE) detectors mounted below the highly tilted samples required for EBSD analyses; these “forward scatter” or “forescatter” detectors also generated images based on the channelling of electrons in crystal lattice planes, giving rise to orientation contrast images. The field of ECCI covers all of these approaches, but it is nowadays most commonly used with the sample being in relatively low-tilt geometries, with the BSEs collected using pole-piece mounted detectors.

To understand Electron Channeling Contrast Imaging (ECCI), it is helpful to examine the physics of electron beam interactions with a crystal. When high-energy primary electrons from a scanning electron microscope (SEM) penetrate a crystalline sample, they generate a standing electron-density wave within the lattice. This wave, known as the primary wave field, remains coherent with the crystal structure (Reimer, (1998)). Depending on the direction of the primary electron beam with respect to the lattice, the maxima of the electron density waves may shift from a position at the atomic nuclei to one in between them. In the first scenario, strong backscattering of electrons occurs from the primary wave field, whereas in the second, only a small number of electrons are backscattered (Goldstein et al., 2017). This difference means that the backscatter signal reveals information about the crystal lattice and its orientation relative to the primary beam (Humphreys, (2001)).

Minimum backscattering happens when the primary beam aligns closely with the Bragg angle of a lattice plane, allowing electrons to penetrate deeply into the crystal with minimal interaction. This phenomenon is known as electron channeling. If a defect, such as a dislocation, is present in the crystal, the coherency of the channeling primary electron wave field with the lattice is disturbed, and strong backscattering occurs near the position of the defect. As a result, the defect is visible as a bright feature on an otherwise dark background when the sample is observed with a backscatter electron detector (See Figure 2) (Schwartz et al., (2009)).

Figure 2: Concept of channeling in Electron Channeling Contrast Imaging (ECCI). A. Guitton: <https://www.antoine-guitton.fr/electron-microscopies-2/>

ECCI is used extensively for performing detailed characterisations of crystalline materials, including metals, ceramics and semiconductors. The main application of ECCI is here for the characterisation of defects in electronic and optoelectronic devices, in particular threading dislocations in GaN, as shown in the Figure 3 below. Vertical threading dislocations appear as local spots with black-white (B-W) contrast; The figure shows an electron channelling contrast micrograph acquired for a GaN semiconductor thin film.

Figure 3: Electron channelling contrast micrograph for a GaN film, the image shows dislocations (local spots with black-white contrast) and atomic steps (lines). Variations in grey scale indicates local variations in the tilt angle.

3.2 Electron Backscatter Diffraction - EBSD

Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD) is an SEM-based non-destructive technique used for detailed material characterization (Schwartz et al., (2009)). In EBSD, an electron beam is scanning the surface of a tilted crystalline sample, where the diffracted electrons at each point create a so-called Kikuchi pattern that can be captured and analyzed with dedicated hardware and software.

This indexing process at each point provides information on the phase, grain boundaries, dislocations, and crystallographic orientation, allowing for an accurate reconstruction of the microstructure. The resulting map reveals details of grain morphology, orientations, and boundaries, while also indicating the preferred crystal orientation (texture) within the sample. Through EBSD, a comprehensive and quantitative representation of the sample's microstructure can be achieved.

In EBSD, the crystalline sample is positioned in the SEM chamber at a steep tilt from the horizontal, typically around 70° , and the electron beam is focused on a small spot on the sample surface (Schwartz et al., (2009)). The incident electrons interact with atoms near the surface (usually within the top 10-200 nm), scattering in various directions while losing only a small portion of their energy. Some of these scattered electrons strike the crystal lattice planes in a way that fulfills the conditions for Bragg diffraction (Reimer & Scanning Electron Microscopy, (1998)).

The diffracted electrons produce pairs of curved lines corresponding to each lattice plane, known as "Kikuchi lines," which together form "Kikuchi bands" (named after Japanese physicist Seishi Kikuchi) (Kikuchi, (1928)). Since crystals contain many lattice planes, the resulting "diffraction pattern" comprises multiple overlapping Kikuchi bands, creating the so-called Kikuchi pattern. This pattern, generated through the EBSD technique, is also commonly referred to as an electron backscatter diffraction pattern (EBSP) (Schwartz et al., (2009)) (see Figure 4). By analysing changes in the diffraction patterns at specific points, EBSD can highlight the effects of lattice distortions caused by defects, such as dislocations.

Figure 4: (a) A typical geometry for EBSD, showing the tilted sample and the EBSP projected at the end of the EBSD detector. (b) A typical high-quality EBSP, with multiple overlapping Kikuchi bands. From EBSD.com

Chapter 4 Field dislocation mechanics (FDM) and

FFT solver

4.1 Field dislocation mechanics (FDM) model

The FDM model used here (Acharya, A. (2001)) can represent discrete dislocation lines as equivalent continuous spatial distributions of dislocation density in a 3D material volume. Here, the dislocation density corresponding to given dislocations will be assigned on a regular voxel grid. This model allows to model any dislocation configuration with the effect of free surfaces, and will be numerically approximated by a fast Fourier transform (FFT) based algorithm. As outputs, the model provides elastic fields, such as strain, rotation and stress fields. It is further used to generate virtual curvature and associated geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) density maps that can be typically measured in EBSD to characterize dislocations and imaged by ECCI. By using the FDM model, we want to investigate the impact of free surfaces on the elastic signatures of threading dislocations in GaN, by comparison with bulk signatures, to evaluate their potential influence on dislocation detection and characterization using surface diffraction-based techniques.

In the FDM model, dislocations are characterized by the Nye tensor α (Nye, J. F. (1953)), also referred to as “geometrically necessary” dislocation (GND) density tensor in the literature. In a Cartesian reference frame (e_1, e_2, e_3), its components $\alpha_{ij} = b_i t_j$ correspond to a Burgers vector length in direction i per unit surface of resolution, for a dislocation line in direction j . For an edge dislocation with a Burgers vector along the e_1 direction, and a dislocation line along the e_3 direction, it corresponds to a dislocation density α_{13} . The density α_{33} will represent a screw dislocation line aligned with the e_3 direction. A mixed dislocation will consist of a combination of both edge and screw dislocation densities.

Figure 5: Numerical setup to model discrete dislocation lines as equivalent continuous spatial distributions of dislocation density on a regular 3D voxel grid with the effect of free surfaces. See text for details. Timmo Weidner et al 2024 Modelling Simul. Mater. Sci. Eng. 32 015004.

The Figure 5 presents an illustrative example of our FFT numerical setup developed to model elastic fields of threading dislocation lines with the effect of free surfaces. In the Figure 5(a), a sketch of a foil is shown, with a vertical screw threading dislocation located at the center, represented by a solid black line. The line vector (denoted \mathbf{t} in the figure, with $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{u}$) and the Burgers vector \mathbf{b} are indicated in the figure. The Figure 5(b) shows the associated Nye tensor component α_{33} distributed on the FFT voxel grid, by using the regularization procedure proposed in (Bertin, N. (2019)). In the same figure, it can be seen how the external free surfaces of a foil are created in the present FDM-FFT simulation. Bright voxels compose the foil material, while dark voxels compose the so-called gas phase. The gas phase has a very small elastic stiffness (typically 10000 times smaller than the foil material) to ensure zero-traction stress boundary conditions at the free surfaces. As an example, the Figure 5(c) shows the stress field σ_{23} surrounding the dislocation line, which tends to zero when reaching the free surfaces. Finally, the Figure 5(d) shows the elastic strain ε_{12} generated in the vicinity of and at the free surfaces. This latter shear strain field is not expected for an infinite straight screw dislocation line. It is the direct consequence of the screw dislocation line reaching the free surface.

Our focus is now on explaining how estimating the internal elastic fields in the FDM model, for any given input dislocation density. We consider a small-strain framework. For further information, the reader is referred to references (Djaka, et al. (2017)) and (Weidner, Timmo, et al. (2023)). In the presence of dislocations, there is a lattice incompatibility. A measure of this incompatibility is the Burgers vector, denoted as \mathbf{b} . It can be written as:

$$\mathbf{b} = \int_C \mathbf{U}^e \cdot d\mathbf{r}. \quad (1)$$

In the above equation, C represents a Burgers circuit that encloses one dislocation line (or more), and \mathbf{U}^e is the elastic distortion. As previously mentioned, we use the Nye's dislocation density tensor to continuously represent dislocations in the model. Consider a surface S , delimited by the circuit C and with a unit normal vector \mathbf{n} , on which the Nye tensor is distributed (dislocation lines intersect the surface S). The net Burgers vector of dislocations can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{b} = \int_S \boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \mathbf{n} \, dS. \quad (2)$$

By applying Stokes's theorem to Eq. (1) and comparing it with Eq. (2), we find that the Nye tensor is related to the elastic distortion, as follows:

$$\mathbf{curl} \mathbf{U}^e = \boldsymbol{\alpha}. \quad (3)$$

This equation implies that the presence of a dislocation density within a material induces elastic distortions. The equation also immediately leads to a conservation law:

$$\mathbf{div} \boldsymbol{\alpha} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (4)$$

This equation means that dislocation lines cannot end inside the material. If there are no dislocations and the Burgers vector is null, there is no lattice incompatibility, and the distortion can be written as the gradient of the elastic displacement vector \mathbf{w} :

$$\mathbf{U}^e = \mathbf{grad}(\mathbf{w}). \quad (5)$$

In the presence of dislocations and incompatibility, the distortion must contain an incompatible part related to Eq. (3). To obtain a unique solution for the elastic distortion for any given dislocation density, we use the Stokes–Helmholtz orthogonal decomposition. \mathbf{U}^e is written as the sum of an incompatible part, the rotational of a field χ (periodic tensor field), and a compatible part, the gradient of the elastic displacement vector \mathbf{w} :

$$\mathbf{U}^e = \mathbf{U}^{e,\perp} + \mathbf{U}^{e,\parallel} = \mathbf{curl}(\chi) + \mathbf{grad}(\mathbf{w}). \quad (6)$$

The elastic distortion resumes to the compatible, gradient part, in the absence of dislocations, while the incompatible, curl part, is related to the Nye tensor α through the incompatibility equation

$$\mathbf{curl}(\mathbf{U}^{e,\perp}) = \alpha = \mathbf{curl}(\mathbf{curl}(\chi)). \quad (7)$$

In the above equation, we used the identity $\mathbf{curl} \mathbf{grad}(\mathbf{w}) = \mathbf{0}$. Also, since $\mathbf{div} \mathbf{curl} \chi = \mathbf{0}$, we have:

$$\mathbf{div} \mathbf{U}^{e,\perp} = \mathbf{0}. \quad (8)$$

Now using the identity $\mathbf{curl} \mathbf{curl} \mathbf{U}^{e,\perp} = \mathbf{grad} \mathbf{div} \mathbf{U}^{e,\perp} - \mathbf{div} \mathbf{grad} \mathbf{U}^{e,\perp}$, and using Eq. (8), the incompatible elastic distortion is the solution of the following Poisson-type equation:

$$\mathbf{div} \mathbf{grad} \mathbf{U}^{e,\perp} = -\mathbf{curl} \alpha. \quad (9)$$

In component form, Eq. (9) reads:

$$U_{ij,kk}^{e,\perp} = -e_{jkl} \alpha_{il,k}. \quad (10)$$

The above equation can be solved for any given input dislocation density to obtain the incompatible elastic distortion. The compatible elastic distortion $\mathbf{U}^{e,\parallel}$ is not involved in this incompatibility problem. As presented below, the compatible part ensures the balance of stresses inside the volume, written here in the absence of volume forces and dynamical effects:

$$\mathbf{div}(\sigma) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (11)$$

In the above, σ is the Cauchy stress tensor. It is related to elastic strains through the Hooke's law:

$$\sigma = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e, \quad (12)$$

Where \mathbf{C} is the fourth-order elastic stiffness tensor and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^e$ is the elastic strain tensor (the symmetric part of the elastic distortion tensor \mathbf{U}^e). By using Eqs. (6) and (11), Eq. (12) can be rewritten as:

$$\mathbf{div}(\sigma) = \mathbf{div}(\mathbf{C} : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\perp})) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (13)$$

In Eq. (13), the quantity $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^\perp = \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\perp}$ represents the stress field related to incompatible elastic strains, which are obtained from the resolution of the incompatibility Eq. (9). To solve equation (13) for the compatible elastic distortion within an FFT numerical framework, we follow the work described in (Djaka, et al. (2017)). Eq. (13) can be solved by an integral Lippmann-Schwinger equation for the unknown compatible elastic strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}$ (elasticity problem) with the additional presence of an incompatible term due to dislocation densities:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}(\mathbf{x}) = \langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel} \rangle - \left(\boldsymbol{\Gamma}^0 \star \boldsymbol{\tau} \right)(\mathbf{x}). \quad (14)$$

In the above, \star denotes the spatial convolution product, \mathbf{x} being a position vector in the FFT periodic unit cell. $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}^0$ is the modified Green tensor associated with an homogeneous reference elastic medium \mathbf{C}^0 . The quantity $\langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel} \rangle$ represents the spatial average of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}$ over the unit cell volume, and $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the stress polarization tensor, defined as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau}(\mathbf{x}) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^\perp(\mathbf{x}) + \delta\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}) : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (15)$$

The tensor $\delta\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{C}^0$. The integral equation (14) and traction boundary conditions on the stress field set an elasticity problem for the unknown field $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel} = (\mathbf{grad} \mathbf{w})^{sym}$. The solution of the implicit equation (14) is given by the following series expansion (Djaka, et al. (2017)):

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} [(-\boldsymbol{\Gamma}^0 \star \delta\mathbf{C})(\mathbf{x})]^n : [\langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel} \rangle - (\boldsymbol{\Gamma}^0 \star \boldsymbol{\sigma}^\perp)(\mathbf{x})]. \quad (16)$$

This series expansion contains an extra term which is a convolution product between the modified Green tensor $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}^0$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^\perp$. Therefore, the numerical FFT algorithm proposed in the next section needs two different procedures, which are the calculation of $\mathbf{U}^{e,\perp}$ from a prescribed dislocation density tensor $\boldsymbol{\alpha}$, and the iterative resolution of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}$, respectively. In the following section, we will employ a fixed-point algorithm, referred to as "basic scheme", following the pioneering work by (Moulinec and Suquet (1994)), to solve Eq. (16), including boundary conditions expressed in terms of tractions.

4.2 Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)-based Algorithm for elasto-static FDM equations

4.2.1 Fourier transform-based method

In the Fourier space, Eq. (10) reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_{ij}^{e,\perp}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) &= i \frac{\xi^k}{\xi^2} e_{jkl} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}_{il}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \quad \forall \boldsymbol{\xi} \neq 0. \\ \tilde{\mathbf{U}}_{ij}^{e,\perp}(0) &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

$\boldsymbol{\xi}$ is the Fourier frequency vector of magnitude $\xi = \sqrt{\boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \boldsymbol{\xi}}$. The complex imaginary number is denoted by i . $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{U}}^{e,\perp}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ are the Fourier transforms of $\boldsymbol{\alpha}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{U}^{e,\perp}(\mathbf{x})$. In the second equation, we impose as a boundary condition that the spatial average of the incompatible elastic distortion is null, to ensure that the incompatibility automatically vanishes in the absence of dislocations. The Fourier transform of the Lippmann-Schwinger equation Eq. (14) yields:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{e,\parallel}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) &= -\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}}^0(\boldsymbol{\xi}) : \tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \quad \forall \boldsymbol{\xi} \neq 0. \\ \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{e,\parallel}(0) &= \langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel} \rangle.\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

In the above equation, $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{e,\parallel}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}}^0(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ are, respectively, the Fourier transform of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}^0(\mathbf{x})$. The components of $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}}^0(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ in the case of isotropic elasticity are given by (Moulinec and Suquet (1998)), In the following simulations, we consider anisotropic and heterogeneous elasticity.

4.2.2 Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)-based algorithm

The FFTW (fast Fourier transform of the west) algorithm is used to calculate both the direct and inverse discrete Fourier transforms on the periodic FFT voxel grid (Frigo, M., & Johnson, S. G. (1997)). The periodic unit cell V is assumed to have spatial dimensions T_1, T_2 and T_3 in the $\mathbf{x}=\mathbf{e}_1$, $\mathbf{y}=\mathbf{e}_2$ and $\mathbf{z}=\mathbf{e}_3$ directions. It is discretized using a 3D grid with $N_1 \times N_2 \times N_3$ voxels. $\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3$ are the voxel sizes in the three directions. The total number of FFT grid points is $N_{tot} = N_1 \times N_2 \times N_3$ and we use $\delta = \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \delta_3$. The discrete Fourier transform (DFT) of a given spatial function f is $\tilde{f} = FFT(f)$. Its inverse Fourier transform is $f = FFT^{-1}(\tilde{f})$.

This section now presents the numerical algorithm employed to solve the elastic fields corresponding to any input dislocation density distribution within a periodic media. This algorithm is presented in (Djaka, et al. (2017)) and recalled here. As aforementioned, it is constituted of two major procedures:

- a) The computation of the incompatible elastic distortion in Fourier space by solving a Poisson-type equation, see Eq. (17), and the initialization of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}$ for a macroscopic imposed stress $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$. In the following simulations where we want to estimate the internal stress fields of dislocations, we impose a very small, negligible value, of one component of $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$, to ensure convergence of the FFT algorithm.
- b) The iterative procedure based on the basic scheme (fixed-point algorithm) to solve Eq. (16), where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}$ is obtained after convergence is reached.

Therefore, the algorithm works as follows:

Initialization procedure: ($\boldsymbol{\alpha}(\mathbf{x})$ being known)

1. The initialization procedure begins with the computation of $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ in the Fourier space by using direct FFT ($\boldsymbol{\alpha}(\mathbf{x})$ is prescribed in the real space).

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\alpha}}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \leftarrow \mathbf{FFT}(\boldsymbol{\alpha})$$

2. Solve Poisson equation Eq. (17) to obtain the incompatible elastic distortion in Fourier space $\tilde{\boldsymbol{U}}^{e,\perp}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$.

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{U}_{ij}^{e,\perp}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) &= i \frac{\xi^k}{\xi^2} e_{jkl} \tilde{\alpha}_{il}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \quad \forall \boldsymbol{\xi} \neq 0 \text{ and} \\ \tilde{U}_{ij}^{e,\perp}(0) &= 0.\end{aligned}$$

3. Computation of the incompatible elastic distortion $\mathbf{U}^{e,\perp}(\mathbf{x})$ in real space by using the inverse FFT.

$$\mathbf{U}^{e,\perp}(\mathbf{x}) \leftarrow \text{FFT}^{-1}(\tilde{\mathbf{U}}^{e,\perp})$$

4. The initialization of the compatible elastic strain $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel}$ for a given macroscopic imposed stress $\bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$.

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0^{e,\parallel} \leftarrow \langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel} \rangle_0 = \mathbf{C}^{0^{-1}} : \bar{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}$$

5. The initialization procedure is concluded by the computation of the initial stress field $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0(\mathbf{x})$ where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\perp}$ is the symmetric part of $\mathbf{U}^{e,\perp}$.

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0(\mathbf{x}) \leftarrow \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}) : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0^{e,\parallel} + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\perp}(\mathbf{x}))$$

Iterative procedure: iterate: $n + 1$ ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^{e,\parallel}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n(\mathbf{x})$ being known)

6. In the global iterative loop at iteration $(n + 1)$, the stress field known from iteration (n) denoted $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n(\mathbf{x})$, is computed in Fourier space by direct FFT to obtain $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_n(\boldsymbol{\xi})$.

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_n(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \text{FFT}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n)$$

7. The precedent stress field is used to test the convergence criterion based on stress equilibrium in the Fourier space. The stress equilibrium convergence criterion used reads:

$$e_n = \frac{\|\text{div}(\boldsymbol{\sigma}_n)\|_2}{|\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma}_n \rangle|} = \frac{\|\boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_n(\boldsymbol{\xi})\|_2}{|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_n(0)|} \leq \epsilon. \quad (19)$$

Where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the norm, $|\cdot|$ is the Euclidian norm of a second order tensor, e_n is the error at iteration n . The convergence is reached when the error is smaller than a given precision ϵ (typically 10^{-5}).

8. The polarization stress tensor $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_n(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ is computed in the Fourier space

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_n(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \leftarrow \tilde{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}_n(\boldsymbol{\xi}) - \mathbf{C}^0 : \widetilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_n^{e,\parallel}}(\boldsymbol{\xi})$$

9. The compatible elastic strain is computed in the Fourier space by Eq. (18)

$$\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1}^{e,\parallel}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \leftarrow -\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}}^0(\boldsymbol{\xi}) : \tilde{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_n(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \quad \forall \boldsymbol{\xi} \neq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1}^{e,\parallel}(\mathbf{0}) \leftarrow \langle \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\parallel} \rangle_n$$

10. The compatible elastic strain is given in the real space from inverse FFT

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{e,\parallel}(\mathbf{x}) \leftarrow \text{FFT}^{-1}(\tilde{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}_{n+1}^{e,\parallel}(\boldsymbol{\xi}))$$

11. The latter is used to update the stress field in the real space. The iterative loop starts again with the updated compatible elastic strain and stress fields until convergence is reached. Then, the total elastic strain (incompatible and compatible parts) and stress fields are finally obtained in the real space.

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}_{n+1}(\mathbf{x}) \leftarrow \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}) : (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{n+1}^{e,\parallel}(\mathbf{x}) + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{e,\perp}(\mathbf{x}))$$

Chapter 5 Volume Vs. surface comparison of dislocation elastic fields: application to threading dislocations in GaN.

5.1 Modeling Setup and Configuration

We now describe how the FFT simulation setup presented above is used to model threading dislocations in a GaN film deposited on a Si substrate, in order to obtain the associated internal elastic fields at the surface and in the bulk. For these simulations, we have chosen to model a large unit cell, with dimensions $15\ \mu\text{m} \times 15\ \mu\text{m}$ in the plane of the film, and a total thickness of $5.1\ \mu\text{m}$. It is shown in Figure 6(a). The FFT grid is composed of $300 \times 200 \times 102$ voxels. The voxel size, i.e., the spatial resolution of FDM, is set to $50\ \text{nm}$ in all directions. This specific setup was selected to capture the relevant spatial features of the threading dislocation fields.

This simulation box consists of three distinct phases, each with specific elastic stiffness tensor \mathbf{C} (see table 1): a GaN layer, a silicon substrate (Si), and a gas phase. As aforementioned, the gas phase (material with very small elastic stiffness), is used to enforce zero-traction stress boundary conditions and mimic a free surface on the top of the GaN layer.

	C_{11} (GPa)	C_{12} (GPa)	C_{13} (GPa)	C_{33} (GPa)	C_{44} (GPa)
GaN	390	145	106	398	105
Silicon	166	63.9	63.9	166	79.6

Table 1: Elastic properties predicted for GaN and Silicon in FDM-FFT calculations, with $C_{11} = C_{22}$; $C_{12} = C_{21}$; $C_{13} = C_{23} = C_{31} = C_{32}$; $C_{44} = C_{55}$. For GaN, and $C_{11} = C_{22} = C_{33}$; $C_{12} = C_{21} = C_{13} = C_{23} = C_{31} = C_{32}$; $C_{44} = C_{55} = C_{66}$

For Si. From (A. Syla and L. Salma, (2016)) and (Ernould, C. et al, (2022)).

Figure 6(b) shows the distribution of dislocation density to model TDs in the GaN layer (dark lines); the dislocation density is defined such that Eq. (2) is satisfied. It is assumed that the GaN film contains six different types of threading dislocations, each represented by a burgers vector \mathbf{b} , and a vertical dislocation line unit vector \mathbf{u} , which cross the GaN layer, from the Si substrate to the free surface of the GaN film. Three dislocation lines perpendicular to the film are edge (<a>-type), screw (<c>-type), and mixed (<a+c>-type) dislocations (the screw dislocation Burgers vector amplitude is $c=5.18\ \text{\AA}$, the one of the edge dislocation is $a=3.18\ \text{\AA}$, while the mixed dislocation contains both edge and screw components). The direction of the dislocation line \mathbf{u} is either parallel to [0001], i.e., the growth direction, or inclined at an angle of 12° from the [0001] direction (Mandal et al., (2024)).

The Figure 6 shows the local internal stress field σ_{11} due to each of the dislocation lines in the film, obtained after convergence of the FDM-FFT numerical algorithm.

Figure 6: The internal stress field σ_{11} of TDs in the 3D FFT grid. (a) Simulation box with a GaN layer deposited on a silicon substrate, and containing a gas phase to reproduce the external free surface on top of the GaN layer. (b) The dislocation density used to model 6 different TDs. The direction of the dislocation line is either parallel to [0001] or approximately 12° from it.

5.2 Comparison of Amplitudes at the surface and in the bulk

To investigate the impact of free surface on the elastic signatures of threading dislocations in GaN, we perform a detailed analysis of the FDM-FFT simulation results. The primary goal of this study is to understand how the presence of free surface influences the elastic fields associated with threading dislocations and how these altered elastic fields differ from those in the bulk material.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 illustrate this comparison by showing computed elastic fields of dislocations, such as strain, rotation and stress fields, as well as the virtual curvature and associated geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) density maps. For the elastic fields at the surface, we refer to Figure 7 [(b), (d), (f), (h)] and Figure 8 [(b), (d), (f), (h)], while Figure 7 [(a), (c), (e), (g)] and Figure 8 [(a), (c), (e), (g)] provide the bulk counterparts. From these Figures, it can be seen that the elastic fields at the surface can differ more or less from those in the bulk material. These differences in amplitudes are summarized in Table 2, which compares the key metric values, highlighting the maximum of elastic fields generated by all dislocations in the simulation box, and reflects the differences observed between the surface and the bulk.

Our findings reveal that the simulated fields and amplitudes can differ significantly between the surface and the bulk. This comparison between surface-affected and bulk dislocation signatures is essential for assessing the accuracy and sensitivity of diffraction-based surface techniques used for the detection and characterization of dislocations in thin films and surface layers. Understanding these surface effects is crucial to accurately interpreting diffraction patterns and dislocation signatures in real GaN applications, as in surface diffraction-based techniques, including ECCI/EBSD that are commonly used for non-destructive analysis of thin films.

These differences in elastic signatures of dislocations at the surface and in the bulk, will serve as a basis for the characterization and identification of threading dislocations, providing a practical tool for analysing threading dislocation types in GaN films, as it is explored in the next sections.

	At the surface	In the bulk at depth 4.2 μm	Percentages %
Max (σ_{vm})	180 MPa	300 MPa	40 % less at the surface
Max (α_{EBSD})	$2.6 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^{-1}$	$2.9 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^{-1}$	10 % less at the surface
Max (ω_{23})	$6.3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ (rad)}$	$5.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ (rad)}$	13 % more at the surface
Max (ω_{31})	$6.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ (rad)}$	$6.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ (rad)}$	3 % less at the surface
Max (ω_{12})	$5.1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ (rad)}$	$6.6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ (rad)}$	22 % less at the surface
Max (α_{13})	$1.0 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^{-1}$	$1.4 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^{-1}$	28 % less at the surface
Max (α_{23})	$7.0 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$	$5.9 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^{-1}$	18 % more at the surface
Max (α_{33})	$2.0 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^{-1}$	$2.2 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^{-1}$	9 % less at the surface

Table 2: Comparison of the maximum Amplitudes between the surface and the bulk.

5.3 Differences in elastic signatures of dislocations at the surface and in the bulk

Figure 7 illustrates the computed elastic fields of dislocations, including strain, rotations, and stress fields, as well as Figure 8 shows the corresponding geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) density maps. In this section, our aim is to describe the various dislocation types signatures and to characterize them both at the surface and within the bulk material, based on the elastic field observations obtained from our simulation.

To characterize a dislocation, it is necessary to determine the burgers vector $\vec{\mathbf{b}}$ and the line dislocation $\vec{\mathbf{u}}$ based on visual comparison of the obtained elastic fields. Specifically, by "characterize," we intend to determine the nature of each dislocation, whether it is an edge, screw, or mixed dislocation.

At the surface, when we look at α_{13} The edge dislocation exhibits symmetric fields. For dislocations with line inclined with respect to [0001], the field shifts leftward. In this scenario, caution is needed when using experimental surface techniques, as the $\langle c \rangle$ dislocations can be interpreted as edge dislocations, i.e., the fields appear as localized spots with some ambiguity likely attributable to surface effects.

When examining α_{33} , the edge dislocations are not detected. $\langle c \rangle$ -type and $\langle a + c \rangle$ -type dislocations are detected, but It is not possible to differentiate the burgers vectors $\vec{\mathbf{b}}$ and the lines $\vec{\mathbf{u}}$, which does not allow dislocations to be characterized, i.e., we cannot differentiate between their field signatures.

When examining α_{EBSD} , all dislocations are detected, but It is not possible to differentiate the burgers vectors $\vec{\mathbf{b}}$ and the lines $\vec{\mathbf{u}}$, i.e., dislocations are not characterized, as the norm of Nye dislocation density serves to generate virtual curvature and associated geometrically necessary dislocation (GND) density maps.

When looking at ω_{31} , $\langle a \rangle$ -type dislocations are not detected. (which is expected since we are specifically searching for $\langle c \rangle$ -type dislocations). Both $\langle c \rangle$ -type and $\langle a + c \rangle$ -type dislocations are detected, the lines $\vec{\mathbf{u}}$ are differentiated, (the field of dislocations with line inclined with respect to [0001], shifts leftward) while the burgers vectors $\vec{\mathbf{b}}$ are not differentiated.

Among our findings, von Mises stress analysis indicates that Pure screw or edge dislocations are challenging to characterize because they can be confused with $\langle c \rangle \parallel [0001]$ and $\langle a \rangle \parallel [0001]$ dislocations. To distinguish between them, the deviation angle needs to exceed 12° .

A dislocation with Burgers vector of $\langle a+c \rangle$ is readily identifiable as a mixed dislocation. A dislocation with a line parallel to $[0001]$ cannot be classified without additional information about its Burgers vector, as it could be either an edge, screw, or mixed dislocation.

Our simulation indicates that dislocation characterization differs at the free surface, as compared to the bulk. In the bulk, it is challenging to precisely characterize each type of dislocation. An exception is found with $\langle a + c \rangle$ -type dislocations, when analyzing strain or stress fields.

Building on the description of dislocation elastic signatures and their characterization, we can identify the key metrics needed to classify each dislocation type, which is explored in the next section.

5.4 Necessary Metrics to identify Different Types of Dislocations and Performing Virtual ECCI

In this section, the goal is to identify and classify the various dislocation types at the surface, and to establish the essential metrics for performing virtual Electron Channelling Contrast Imaging (ECCI). Based on our simulations, characterizing different types of dislocations involves analysing several key elements: strain or stress fields, rotations, and specific components of the Nye dislocation density tensor α_{13} and α_{23} .

As previously mentioned, accurately characterizing a dislocation requires determining both its burgers vector \vec{b} and the dislocation line \vec{u} . For each type of threading dislocation, we analyze the distinct characteristics of its Burgers vector and line vector. These unique features enable us to differentiate each dislocation type from others, as the specific configurations of the Burgers vector and the dislocation line provide distinguishable signatures, allowing us to differentiate one dislocation type from another. The necessary metrics for this classification are summarized in the table below.

	To differentiate the burgers vector \vec{b}	To differentiate the line dislocation \vec{u}	Characterized
$\langle a + c \rangle \parallel [0001]$	ε_{vm} or ω_{12} or α_{23}	And ω_{23} or ω_{31}	✓
$\langle a + c \rangle \# [0001]$	ε_{vm} or ω_{12} or α_{23}	And ω_{23} or ω_{31}	✓
$\langle c \rangle \parallel [0001]$	ε_{vm} or ω_{12} or α_{23}	And ω_{23} or ω_{31}	✓
$\langle c \rangle \# [0001]$	ε_{vm} or ω_{12} or α_{23}	And ω_{23} or ω_{31}	✓
$\langle a \rangle \parallel [0001]$		α_{13}	✓
$\langle a \rangle \# [0001]$	ε_{vm} or ω_{12} or α_{23}	And α_{13}	✓

Table 3: The necessary and sufficient metrics to characterize the different types of dislocations at the surface

In virtual ECCI simulations, it is essential to analyse and export rotational components that deviate from ideal beam perpendicularity, specifically ω_{31} and ω_{23} . These components represent rotations around the crystal axes, with ω_{31} affecting the plane involving axes [3] and [1] and ω_{23} influencing the plane involving axes [2] and [3]. Such deviations are crucial for fine-tuning diffraction conditions, as the electron beam's interaction with the periodic atomic potential is sensitive to orientation.

The dislocation line \vec{u} , which defines the direction of a dislocation within the crystal, can be differentiated using these rotational components. The precise adjustment of ω_{31} and ω_{23} enables visualization and distinction of dislocations based on their geometric orientation relative to the beam.

experimentally, the diffraction vector \mathbf{g} , corresponding to specific lattice planes, plays a key role in determining the Burgers vector \vec{b} , since $I \propto (\mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{b})$ with I is the intensity of backscattered electrons (H. Kriaa et al. (2019)). By leveraging these components, virtual ECCI provides a detailed understanding of dislocations.

Figure 7: Comparisons between the elastic fields of dislocations at the surface (b)-(d)-(f)-(h) and in the bulk (a)-(c)-(e)-(g): (a) von Mises stress σ_{vm} (MPa) in the bulk; (b) von Mises stress σ_{vm} (MPa) at the surface; (c) The rotation around x axis in the bulk of GaN; (d) The rotation around x axis at the surface; (e) The rotation around y axis in the bulk of GaN; (f) The rotation around y axis at the surface; (g) The rotation around z axis in the bulk of GaN; (h) The rotation around z axis at the surface (rad).

Figure 8: Comparisons between the elastic fields of dislocations at the surface (b)-(d)-(f)-(h) and in the bulk (a)-(c)-(e)-(g): (a) The generated virtual curvature α_{EBSD} in the bulk of GaN (m^{-1}); (b) The generated virtual curvature α_{EBSD} at the surface of GaN; (c) the component of Nye dislocation density α_{13} in the bulk of GaN; (d) the component of Nye dislocation density α_{13} at the surface of GaN; (e) the component of Nye dislocation density α_{23} in the bulk of GaN; (f) the component of Nye dislocation density α_{23} at the surface of GaN; (g) the component of Nye dislocation density α_{33} in the bulk of GaN; (h) the component of Nye dislocation density α_{33} at the surface of GaN;

Chapter 6 Summary and Conclusion

A spectral method based on Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) algorithms has been used and applied to solve the elasto-static equations of Field Dislocation Mechanics (FDM) for heterogeneous elastic periodic media, in the case of TDs in a GaN layer deposited on a Si substrate. This approach takes advantage of the computational efficiency of FFT, enabling rapid solutions to complex dislocation problems in heterogeneous materials. The model computes the internal mechanical fields resulting from both elastic heterogeneities and dislocation density, derived by solving Poisson-type and Lippmann–Schwinger equations. These equations are resolved in Fourier space using an iterative algorithm.

To demonstrate the potential of our method, we considered threading dislocations in GaN semiconductor layers along the [0001] direction, deposited on a Si substrate. Our results reveal significant differences in the elastic fields between the surface and bulk regions of the material. This distinction is crucial for assessing the precision and sensitivity of diffraction-based techniques such as Electron Channeling Contrast Imaging (ECCI) and Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD).

Furthermore, our findings provide key metrics for accurately characterizing dislocations at both the surface and within the bulk material. This is also essential for performing virtual ECCI, which correlates simulation data with experimental observations. By integrating computational modeling with experimental techniques, our approach enables precise predictions of dislocation behavior and the high-precision visualization of defects. Furthermore, the simulated profiles serve as a robust reference for identifying experimental counterparts.

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